

MEDICAL SCIENCES

IMPROVEMENT OF THE LIFESPAN OF COMPOSITE RESTORATIONS

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Abstract

Despite the fact that there are currently many adhesive systems, the problem of ensuring a reliable and long-lasting bond between composite materials and the tooth surface has not been fully solved [1,2]. Thanks to advancements in dental materials science, adhesive systems have been classified as a separate class of materials used for restoring hard dental tissues.

Keywords: composite material, hybrid layer, adhesives.

No composite material is used without an adhesive system. The adhesive technique has become widely used in dental practice because it helps to maximize the preservation of tooth tissues, ensures a reliable and durable bond between dental materials and enamel and dentin, and isolates the pulp from all types of irritants [3,5]. Materials differ significantly in their characteristics and application techniques, which requires the dentist to have specific knowledge and constantly improve their skills in adhesive dentistry. Today, dentists face the challenge of finding a balance between the time and labor intensity of adhesive preparation and achieving optimal bonding with the tooth's hard tissues [4].

The connection between dentin and cement occurs through the formation of a hybrid layer with the help of an adhesive system, which is not a true chemical bond but rather a micromechanical bond, ensuring the hermetic sealing of the restoration. The danger of poor marginal sealing lies in the risk of periodontal disease, secondary caries, discoloration of the restoration boundary, postoperative sensitivity, debonding of the restoration, and ultimately an unsuccessful treatment outcome. Numerous studies have confirmed that when using an adhesive system immediately after cavity preparation, the hybrid layer forms more extensively, as the fluid penetrates deeper into the dentinal tubules, forming what is known as "adhesive tags".

The quality of the hybrid layer largely depends on the degree of infiltration of the tooth's hard tissues that were subjected to acid etching. Areas of incomplete infiltration accelerate the hydrolytic degradation of the hybrid layer and contribute to its aging. Furthermore, the high degree of infiltration of micropores and roughness, formed as a result of acid etching of the tooth, is, to some extent, influenced by the time of application of the adhesive to the working surface.

Material and Methods

The study involved 22 extracted teeth, on which 44 restorations were performed. Cavities of a standard-

ized size (depth – 1 mm, diameter – 3 mm) were prepared on the distal and mesial contact surfaces using diamond burs of a specific size and grit. The central part of the formed defects was located at the enamel-cement junction. Artificially prepared cavities were subjected to acid etching according to the manufacturer's instructions using Gluma Etch gel (Heraeus Kulzer). The cavities were then rinsed and dried with a gentle stream of air, followed by the application of a 5th generation adhesive (Prime&Bond NT Dentsply).

In all samples, the adhesive was applied for 20 seconds (according to the manufacturer's instructions) on one contact surface (n=22). On the other contact surface (n=22), a 60-second application was performed, followed by gentle air drying and removal of excess adhesive. The polymerization of the hybrid and adhesive layers was carried out with a Bluephase 20i Ivoclar (Vivadent) LED lamp in High Power mode with a light intensity of 1200 mW/cm² for 20 seconds. After placing the composite restorations (Megafill, Megadenta), the teeth were subjected to thermocycling (500 cycles at temperatures of 5 and 55°C), and the root apices were sealed with sticky wax.

All samples were coated with two layers of nail varnish, leaving a 1 mm margin from the edge of the composite filling, and then immersed in a 1% methylene blue solution for 24 hours. Afterward, the samples were longitudinally cut through the center of the restorations. The quality of bonding between the composite and the hard tooth tissues was evaluated on a scale from 0 to 4 based on the following criteria: no microleakage – 0; microleakage within 1/3 of the wall – 1; microleakage within 2/3 of the wall – 2; microleakage covering the entire wall – 3; microleakage extending to the bottom of the cavity – 4.

Results and Discussion

The assessment of the bonding quality of the composite to the enamel of the tooth, when the adhesive application time was 20 seconds, resulted in 0.41±0.86, while for the 60-second adhesive exposure, it was

0.18±0.31 ($p=0.245$). The evaluation of the bonding quality of the composite to the dentin of the tooth showed that the 20-second adhesive exposure on the etched dentin surface led to the formation of a more uniform bonding layer. However, it is important to critically analyze the obtained data since there is currently no experimental model that can fully simulate the frequency, strength, and direction of debonding stresses that composite restorations experience in the oral cavity over time. Nonetheless, in this study, the subjective bias was minimal, as each tooth sample underwent both adhesive application methods, and the bonding quality was tested simultaneously.

Thus, the 60-second adhesive application on the etched surface resulted in a better quality bond between the composite material and the dentin of the tooth, which was 37% better than the results from the 20-second exposure. The differences in the enamel-composite bonding quality between the two adhesive application methods did not show statistical significance.

Conclusion

It was demonstrated that allowing the adhesive to dry for at least 60 seconds leads to better results than drying the adhesive for 20 seconds.

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